

Problematic Interpretation of the Ipatiev Chronicle:

The Russian Sonderweg Debate

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Abstract

This article examines the Ipatiev Chronicle and its interpretation by Nikolai Karamzin as a foundational text in shaping Russian national identity. It argues that Karamzin's reading of the Chronicle established an ethnocentric narrative of a "unique Russian path," or *Sonderweg*, that paralleled debates about German exceptionalism. By situating the Ipatiev Chronicle within the intellectual currents of nineteenth-century Russian historiography and comparing it with the German *Sonderweg* debate, the article highlights how myths of destiny and cultural singularity were constructed through selective historical interpretation. The analysis shows that the Chronicle, once a medieval monastic record, was transformed into a tool of nation-building, embedding the idea of Russia's historical distinctiveness into both scholarly and popular consciousness. In reframing the Ipatiev Chronicle as both a primary source and a cultural artifact, this paper underscores the methodological challenges of using medieval texts to legitimize modern political narratives.

Keywords: Ipatiev Chronicle, Karamzin, Russian historiography, *Sonderweg*, nationalism, myth of destiny, exceptionalism

December 31, 1999, the last day of the century and the millennium.

The first President of Russia, Boris Yeltsin, abruptly announced his resignation. In his final address to the citizens of Russia, he said, in part:

"...I apologize for not justifying some of the hopes of those people who believed that we could jump from a gray, stagnant, totalitarian past to a bright, rich, civilized future in one spurt, one stroke, one sign. I believed it myself. It seemed that we would conquer everything in one leap. It did not work in one fell swoop. In some ways, I was too naive."

The image of the future that the first president spoke about in his address was linked to the desire to join the community of Western powers, which was widespread in Russia at the end of the 20th century. And yet, in his address - and perhaps in his political calculations as well - Yeltsin reproduced (apparently unconsciously) one of the most fundamental myths of Russian culture, according to which Russia's "special way," its "historical destiny," "place in the world," "unique spirituality" and the comparative advantages and disadvantages of its "backwardness" compared to the West.

Myths of National Destiny

How it is that the discussion of the unique path of Russia has been so alive and powerful throughout several centuries, starting from the publication of Peter Chaadayev's "First Philosophical Letter" in 1836¹ and ending up with the myth about "historical justification" of totalitarianism in modern Russia.

¹ Raymond T. McNally, "The Significance of Chaadayev's Weltanschauung," *Russian Review* 23, no. 4 (October 1964): 352, <https://doi.org/10.2307/126212>.

The discussion about the "uniqueness" and "divine mission" of Russia on Earth bloomed on a very fertile historical land. The long nineteenth century in Russia came just after Peter The Great's reforms and the start of diplomatic relationships. The so-called "open window" to Europe catalyzed the inevitable comparison process and the "us versus them" mentality². After the Napoleonic Wars (the 1820s), when the Russian state and the Russian nobles began to diverge, elite Russian people started to painfully look into the vast and threatening peasant masses³, trying to understand whether it hides the mysteries of Russia's world-historical destiny, which worried them.

And in this search for answers Nikolay Karamzin, a Russian Imperial historian, published the fundamental *History of the Russian State*, a 12-volume national history where he interprets several primary sources; however, the one we are most interested in is the *Ipatiev Chronicle* — Karamzin was the first who found and interpreted this source. The publication of the first volumes of "History" had a stunning effect on its contemporaries. Pushkin's generation read his work enthusiastically, discovering the past's unknown pages. Writers and poets developed memorable stories into works of fiction.

Thus, considering the colossal influence of Karamzin's historical work based on the Ipatiev Chronicle on Nobles of Russia in the 20s and 30s descendants of the 19th century, we can assume that the ideas of Westerners and Slavophiles that occurred at the same time can be associated with each other. So, the logical question to ask would be: *What was the role and*

² People's tendency to view the social world in terms of ingroup ("us") and outgroup ("them").

³ In 1858, there were 19 million state peasants and 22.5 million private serfs.

significance of the Ipatiev Chronicle in building the “unique Russian path” idea in the 1830s by the nobles?

Ipatiev Chronicle as Primary Source

Ipatiev Chronicle⁴ was created in Kyiv in the 1110s. It is written in Old Russian of the Church Slavic language. After its discovery, it has been the primary basis for the history of ancient Russia.⁵

Contradictory, modern historians, like Igor Yeregin, struggle to use it as a reliable source:

"When we begin to read the Tale Chronicle, we find ourselves in a completely mysterious world in which everything is incomprehensible."⁶

The Chronicle's author was Nestor Pechersky — the representative of the only literate class in Ancient Rus, clergy — with the main aim of promoting God's will. The chronicler seems interested in the question: what would it mean? He does not try to explain to his readers how it was but what it was. He integrates his history into the sacred account — a continuation of the

⁴Also known as Нуратіан Letopis; Belarusian: Іпацьеўскі летапіс; Russian: Ипатьевская летопись; Ukrainian: Іпатіївський літопис.

⁵“Ipatiev Chronicle - COMPLETE COLLECTION of RUSSIAN CHRONICLES,” web.archive.org, August 1, 2020, https://web.archive.org/web/20200801192819/http://www.lrc-lib.ru/rus_letopisi/Ipatius/contents.htm.

⁶Igor Yeregin, *Lectures on Ancient Russian Literature. 1968, “ImWerden”, электронная библиотека Андрея Никитина-Перенского* (1968; repr., Leningrad: Leningrad University Press, 1968), https://imwerden.de/pdf/eregin_lektsii_po_drevnej_russkoj_literature_1968_ocr.pdf.

holy history, repeating it to some extent. Therefore, he often quotes directly or indirectly from biblical texts and adapts the events he records to them.

This is a very serious point because the Ipatiev Chronicle has been characterized differently. The hand of the chronicler was guided not by abstract ideas about the truth but by worldly passions and political interests. Moreover, the monk likely was a servant of the court chancellery of a prince who did not stop at distorting the folk tradition and rearranging events, and putting a false date.

This rather sly installation leads us to the tough conclusion that the Chronicle is an artificial and unreliable source. However, starting from Karamzin's first interpretation, the text continues to be used as the primary source on the early history of Ancient Rus though many data have a legendary plot.

Figure 1. *A Page from the Hypatian Chronicle (Khlebnikov Manuscript)*. n.d.

Http://Www.encyclopediaofukraine.com/Picturedisplay.asp?Linkpath=Pic%5CH%5CY%5CHypatian%20Chronicle%20(Khlebnikov%20Manuscript).Jpg&Page=Pages%5CH%5CY%5CHypatianChronicle.htm&Id=4797&Pid=12612&Tyt=Hypatian%20Chronicle&Key=Hypatian+Chronicle.

Karamzin's Interpretation

The ethnocentric basis of knowledge production⁷ is prominent not only in the Chronicle creation process but also in its interpretation by Karamzin, N. (1812) in his fundamental work *History of the Russian State*.

First, no matter what form of knowledge we focus on, its validation is grounded in objectification processes. In other words, Karamzin's interpretation would not have been pushed forth unless Karamzin's power and privilege⁸. During his work in the silence of the archives, a significant shift in his worldview of Karamzin took place in the direction of conservatism. He believed in an etatist⁹ picture of the world and the efficacy of autocracy.

"While preserving the cult of virtue and sentiment, he was imbued with patriotism and the cult of the state. He concluded that to be successful; the state must be strong, monarchical, and autocratic."¹⁰

⁷ John H. Stanfield, "The Ethnocentric Basis of Social Science Knowledge Production," *Review of Research in Education* 12 (1985): 387, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1167154>.

⁸ Karamzin, N was a noble thriving in the imperialistic feudal ideas of the state. He also was one of the closest people to Emperor Alexander I.

⁹ Etatism refers to the fact that state attempts to determine, the societal structure and social life.

¹⁰ Nikolai Karamzin, *About Ancient and New Russia in Its Political and Civil Relations*, *Www.prlib.ru* (Berlin: F. Schneider, 1861 (Naumburg), 1861), <https://www.prlib.ru/en/node/429777>.

While filling some historical gaps in the Chronicle, Karamzin produced other historical silences. He followed the development of the supreme power, which gradually took the form of his modern autocracy and neglected the history of the Russian people itself. In his work, he acted more as a writer than a historian - describing historical facts, he cared about creating a new noble language for the conduct of the historical narrative. For example, describing the first centuries of Russia described in the Chronicle, Karamzin said:

"Great nations, like great men, have their infancy and should not be ashamed of it: our fatherland, weak, divided into small areas until the year 862, according to the chronology of Nestor, owes its greatness to the happy introduction of monarchical power."¹¹

Moreover, Karamzin was one of the pioneers of classicism in Literature, and its traditions can be seen throughout his entire work: in the tradition of classicism, the author often concludes the narrative of a historical episode with a moralistic maxim or emotional digression.

Karamzin uses comparative lenses when interpreting the Ipatiev Chronicle. By asking clear-cut questions referring to the change or stagnation in the early development of Rus (e.g., Why did Moscow become the center of Orthodox Christianity? Why there were "Vague Times" after the death of Ivan IV?), the historian falls into the false idea of Russia being an autonomous country, disregarding profound internal relationships (e.g., Russian Emperor family ties with many European royal monarchies, wars, and international trade) and the constant imperialist process of land acquisition. So the narrative of uniqueness populates his texts in a way that presents the whole of Russian society to have departed from some standard trajectory to follow a deviant path.

¹¹ Nikolai Karamzin, *About Ancient and New Russia in Its Political and Civil Relations*, *Www.prlib.ru* (Berlin: F. Schneider, 1861 (Naumburg), 1861), <https://www.prlib.ru/en/node/429777>.

Bigger Picture

Emperor Alexander I, who sponsored Karamzin's study of the Chronicle, was highly influenced by the "lessons" of the text about the uniqueness of the Russian path a couple of years after the publication of History of the Russian State, the new official ideology — "Orthodoxy, Autocracy, Nationality."¹² According to this idea, the uniqueness of the Russian path entails Russia's main advantage: its backwardness. It predicted a transformational breakthrough for their country that would one day help it lead the world community of powers. This idea proved unusually attractive to thinkers, writers, and politicians who were otherwise very dissimilar and even opposed to one another.

In external politics, Alexander I and following autocrats would follow this idea by presenting Imperialist wars as a way to defend the Slavic Christians.¹³

Deutscher Sonderweg

Looking at world history, we can notice a similar attempt to build the concept of uniqueness and identity in the German Theory of Deutscher Sonderweg. It goes back to Fichte's "Speeches to the German Nation," written in 1806, an outstanding monument of German philosophy and an essential milestone in the formation of German self-awareness. Fichte generally believed that language is the force that unites a nation around itself.¹⁴ And this

¹² It was formulated and spread by Minister of National Education Sergei Uvarov in 1832.

¹³ E.g., Russian-Turkish wars of the 19th century, or the Crimean War in 1854.

¹⁴ Fichte Johann Gottlieb. 1924. Reden an Die Deutsche Nation. Leipzig: A. Kröner.

cultural-spiritual nationalism was also perceived by Russian Slavophiles in their interpretation. Fichte generally believed that language is the force that unites a nation around itself. And this cultural-spiritual nationalism was also perceived by Russian Slavophiles in their interpretation.

If, according to Hegel, the "absolute spirit" is embodied in history (Hegel, 1770-1831), the Slavophiles sought forms of the "folk spirit" in concrete structures: in beards, songs, and ancient customs. The penetration of Hegel's philosophy into Russian public life gave rise to a unique phenomenon - a kind of "Orthodox Hegelianism," which became the foundation of Slavophilism. As usual with us, Western forms included Russian national content.

The paradox of the Chronicle and Karamzin's History of the Russian State is a gap in the knowledge about international relations or its ethnocentric representation, belittling its importance, and silencing the peasantry, the majority of the population.

In conclusion, The Ipatiev Chronicle was or was not fictitious or exaggerated to achieve certain goals: religious or state (although at the time of writing this source, statehood was based on religion) — due to a lack of information from research, we cannot say for sure. However, the chronicle is not as important as how it was decided to interpret it. The discovery of the chronicle came at the time of the patriotic rise of Russia and the desire of the aristocrats to explain the backwardness of the country with its multimillion peasantry population. And Karamzin gave them this answer — Russia just has a unique path and this backwardness is actually nothing else but the advantage and sign of superiority. However, was this conclusion reached based on the text of the Chronicle or made up because of confirmation bias and biased content of the slavic text?

Thus, answering the stated in the beginning question, the Ipatiev Chronicle had an indirect and insufficient but very influential role in building the “unique Russian path” a idea in the 1830s by the nobles. However, the works of the mediator between the Chronicle and the nobles were already sufficient to set conditions that produced the new concept in the national consciousness.

Generation after generation of Russian people, their ideologists, and leaders have reproduced the ethnocentric text of Karamzin based on no less ethnocentric Chronicle. The more horrible and hopeless the present day, the stronger and more treacherous the enemies, and the more impressive and evident will be the flight of the Flying Troika¹⁵.

¹⁵ Troika is usually a Russian sleigh pulled by three horses, harnessed in manners, invented in the 17th century, which allowed it to travel at an unprecedented speed for that time in the snowy barrens of the country (Vinay Shukla, “The Flying Troika,” Russia Beyond (Russia Beyond, October 3, 2022).

The sentence is a reference to a metaphor of Nikolai Gogol in his novel, *Dead Souls*, where he compares Russia with Troika:

“Oh troika, winged troika, tell me who invented you? Surely, nowhere but among a nimble nation could you have been born in a country which has taken itself in earnest and has evenly spread far and wide over half of the globe, so that once you start counting the milestones you may count on till a speckled haze dances before your eyes... Rus, are you not similar in your headlong motion to one of those nimble troikas that none can overtake? The flying road turns into smoke under you, bridges thunder and pass, all fall back and is left behind!... And what does this awesome motion mean? What is the passing strange steeds! Has the whirlwind a home in your manes?... Rus, whither are you speeding to? Answer me. No answer. The middle bell trills out in a dream its liquid soliloquy; the roaring air is torn to pieces and becomes wind; all things on earth fly by and other nations and states gaze askance as they step aside and give her the right of way.”

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